

Reference List for the DFG grant: Röhner, J. (2024). Durch die multimethodale Lupe künstlicher Intelligenz und qualitativer Inhaltsanalyse: Effekte von Intelligenz und Geschlechtsrollen-Selbstkonzept auf Antwortmuster und Bestandteile des kognitiven Prozesses beim Verfälschen [Through a multimethod lens of artificial intelligence and qualitative content analyses: Effects of intelligence and gender on response patterns and elements of the cognitive process of faking].

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This document contains the full reference list from the DFG grant: “Durch die multimethodale Lupe künstlicher Intelligenz und qualitativer Inhaltsanalyse: Effekte von Intelligenz und Geschlechtsrollen-Selbstkonzept auf Antwortmuster und Bestandteile des kognitiven Prozesses beim Verfälschen [Through a multimethod lens of artificial intelligence and qualitative content analyses: Effects of intelligence and gender on response patterns and elements of the cognitive process of faking]”. The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

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